

Diversity and global citizenship in the university: is university training contributing to their mastery?

Diversidad y ciudadanía global en la universidad ¿la formación universitaria contribuye a su dominio?

Aim

To describe students' perceptions of whether their university is raising awareness of the importance of diversity and global citizenship education (D&GC) and its association with selected socio-demographic and academic variables.

To be able to introduce changes in university training programmes that respond to current demands in this area.

Research Questions

- RQ1: Are universities raising awareness of diversity and global citizenship?
- RQ2: How often do universities address various issues related to diversity and global citizenship through workshops, courses, roundtables, seminars, training, etc.?
- RQ3: Are students willing to broaden their knowledge through training courses on diversity and global citizenship?

Methodology

❑ **Sample:** 913 observations from 5 European universities: Finland, Germany, Spain, Romania and Lithuania.

❑ **Measures:** questionnaire containing 2 parts.

- Part 1: socio-demographic and academic factors.
- Part 2: questions related to:
 - ✓ Students' perception of how their university approaches D&CG awareness and training.
 - ✓ Frequency with which their university held a training course on D&CG-related topics.

❑ **Procedure and data analysis:** Questionnaire distributed through the platforms of the 5 universities.

Tests: descriptive statistics and Pearson Chi-square test to determine the association between variables..

Socio-demographic and academic variables	Definition
Country of residence	1: Finland; 2: Germany; 3: Spain; 4: Romania; 5: Lithuania; 6: Others.
Gender	1: Male; 2: Female; 3: Diverse.
Age	1: 17-23 years; 2: 24-30 years; 3: over 31 years.
Knowledge area studies	1: Social and Legal Sciences; 2: Engineering and Architecture; 3: Health Sciences; 4: Arts and Humanities; 5: Sciences.
Educational level	1: Bachelor's degree; 2: Master's degree; 3: PhD.

Variables on Diversity and Global Citizenship	Definition
University awareness of D&CG	1: Yes; 2: No.
Frequency with which your university deals with various issues related to DyCG.	1: Very often; 2: Quite often; 3: Sometimes; 4: Rarely; 5: Never. Themes: -Peace education. -Cultural Awareness. -Support for democracy. -Discrimination based on age. -Human rights. -LGBTQI+ Rights. -Preventing extremism. -People with disabilities. -Climate change. -Gender equality. -Prevention of racism.
Importance of courses DyCG	1: Very important; 2: Important; 3: Neutral; 4: Something important; 5: Not important.
Course format DyCG	1: Online; 2: Hybrid (online with real-time webinars); 3: On-site

Results

		Percentage	
Frequencies	University awareness of D&CG	Yes	69,7
		No	30,3
	-Peace education.	Very often	9,3
		Quite often	17,2
		Sometimes	34,1
		Rarely	20,4
		Never	19,1
	-Cultural Awareness.	Very often	17
		Quite often	22,9
		Sometimes	33
Rarely		17	
	Never	10,2	
-Support for democracy.	Very often	14,1	
	Quite often	22,8	
	Sometimes	32,4	
	Rarely	16,8	
	Never	13,9	
-Discrimination based on age.	Very often	10,3	
	Quite often	13,1	
	Sometimes	28	
	Rarely	22	
	Never	26,5	
-Human rights.	Very often	19,6	
	Quite often	24,1	
	Sometimes	28,8	
	Rarely	16,1	
	Never	11,4	

		Percentage
-LGBTQI+ Rights.	Very often	11,6
	Quite often	13,6
	Sometimes	25,7
	Rarely	20,6
	Never	28,5
-Preventing extremism.	Very often	8
	Quite often	13,5
	Sometimes	31,9
	Rarely	22,2
	Never	24,4
-People with disabilities.	Very often	14,6
	Quite often	21,9
	Sometimes	29,6
	Rarely	18,4
	Never	15,6
-Climate change.	Very often	15,3
	Quite often	24
	Sometimes	30,3
	Rarely	18
	Never	12,4
-Gender equality.	Very often	18,3
	Quite often	22,9
	Sometimes	29,5
	Rarely	15,9
	Never	13,5
-Prevention of racism.	Very often	15,3
	Quite often	21
	Sometimes	28,3
	Rarely	19,1
	Never	16,3

		Percentage
Importance of courses DyCG	Very important	24,8
	Important	31,4
	Neutral	23,5
	Something	10,4
	Not important	9,9
Course format DyCG	Online	33,7
	Hybrid	45
	On-site	21,2

Results

Association between student perception of university awareness of D&CG and socio-demographic and academic factors.

χ^2 Pearson	University awareness of D&CG
	Sig.
Country of residence	0,001**
Gender	No sig.
Age	No sig.
Knowledge area studies	0,001**
Educational level	No sig.

N: 913; **p<0,01

Results

Association between the frequency with which the university addresses various D&CG-related topics through workshops, courses, round tables, seminars, trainings, etc. and socio-demographic and academic factors.

χ^2 Pearson	-Peace education. Sig.	χ^2 Pearson	-Discrimination based on age. Sig.	χ^2 Pearson	-Preventing extremism. Sig.	χ^2 Pearson	-Gender equality. Sig.
Country of residence	0,001**	Country of residence	0,001**	Country of residence	0,001**	Country of residence	No sig.
Gender	No sig.	Gender	No sig.	Gender	0,034*	Gender	No sig.
Age	0,001**	Age	No sig.	Age	0,017*	Age	No sig.
Knowledge area studies	0,001**	Knowledge area studies	No sig.	Knowledge area studies	0,029*	Knowledge area studies	No sig.
Educational level	No sig.	Educational level	No sig.	Educational level	No sig.	Educational level	No sig.
	-Cultural Awareness.		-Human rights.		-People with disabilities.		-Prevention of racism.
Country of residence	0,001**	País residencia	No sig.	Country of residence	0,023*	Country of residence	No sig.
Gender	No sig.	Gender	No sig.	Gender	No sig.	Gender	No sig.
Age	No sig.	Age	No sig.	Age	0,001**	Age	No sig.
Knowledge area studies	0,001**	Knowledge area	0,002**	Knowledge area studies	0,006**	Knowledge area studies	0,040*
Educational level	No sig.	Educational level		Educational level	No sig.	Educational level	0,039*
	-Support for democracy.		LGBTBTQI+ Rights		-Climate change.		
Country of residence	0,001**	Country of residence	0,001**	Country of residence	0,001**		
Gender	No sig.	Gender	No sig.	Gender	No sig.		
Age	No sig.	Age	0,012*	Age	0,011*		
Knowledge area studies	0,001**	Knowledge area studies	No sig.	Knowledge area studies	No sig.		
Educational level	No sig.	Educational level	No sig.	Educational level	0,001**		

N: 913; *p<0,05; **p<0,01

Results

Association between the degree of importance given by students to taking D&CG courses and socio-demographic and academic factors.

χ^2 Pearson	Importance of courses
	DyCG
	Sig.
Country of residence	0,002**
Gender	0,021*
Age	No sig.
Knowledge area	0,010**
Educational level	No sig.

N: 913; **p<0,01

Association between D&CG course format preference and socio-demographic and academic factors.

χ^2 Pearson	Course format
	DyCG
	Sig.
Country of residence	0,001**
Gender	No sig.
Age	0,002**
Knowledge area studies	0,001**
Educational level	No sig.

N: 913; **p<0,01

Conclusions

- ❑ A high percentage of the surveyed students (69.7%) perceive that their university is raising awareness on D&CG.
- ❑ In relation to the frequency with which universities address the eleven topics related to Diversity and Global Citizenship through courses or workshops, it seems that it is not very common for them to do so in this format.
- ❑ A large proportion of the students surveyed (56%) consider it important or very important for universities to run D&CG courses, and the majority prefer these courses to have a hybrid format (online with real-time webinars).
- ❑ With regard to the existence of differences according to a set of socio-demographic and academic factors and the three main variables analysed, we observed the existence of a significant association, above all according to the students' country of residence and the area of knowledge they study.

In conclusion:

It could be of interest to design and deliver courses on D&CG on an ongoing basis as a complement to the extracurricular training of students.

Thank you! / ¡Gracias!

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